

STACK: stages of the process through the beginner's experience

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Abstract: The academics of Centre for Sciences at TTK University of Applied Sciences (TTK UAS) have been trying different types of questions in online tests in order to considerably facilitate the work of the academics and increase students' opportunities for independent study and for the feedback. Since 2017 STACK questions type expanded the existing online math at TTK UAS and provided new possibilities to computer aided assessment (CAA). This article presents presents "useful finds" through the beginner's eyes.

Keywords: automatic assessment, e-assessment, teaching and learning of Mathematics, mathematical education.

1 Introduction

In recent times online tests turned on to a powerful and widespread tool for teaching and learning. In higher education recommended to use online tests resources for assessments and self-test as well. According to [JGB05] and [SJS08] e-assessment is a highly useful tool that can stimulate thinking skills and facilitate deep learning. Higher education in Estonia also went along with this trend. The digital revolution in Estonia is aimed at the more productive introduction of modern digital technologies in teaching, research, education and the development of the digital skills of the whole nation. Since 1997 Information Technology Foundation for Education (HITSA) was founded. The role of the HITSA is to ensure that the graduates at all levels of education have obtained digital skills necessary for the development of economy and society and the possibilities offered by ICT are skilfully used in teaching and learning, which helps to improve the quality of learning and teaching at all levels of education. And in 2003 Foundation Innove was created by the Ministry of Education and Research. Innove has a powerful web-based testing platform used nationwide. Innove systematically supports the creation of online tests. Most of them are freely available and can be used by bookkeepers or students throughout the country [In20]. Also, in every educational institution in Estonia there is a person called educational technologist, who supports teachers in creating online materials and, as a rule, introduces new technologies, including technologies for creating

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and using online tests. According to the authors, there are three universities in Estonia that currently use the STACK question type [Sa03]. These universities are participating in the ABACUS project [Ra16].

In this paper the authors briefly describe the history of the use and development of online tests at TTK University of Applied Sciences (TTK UAS), from creating simple tests till inculcation and elaboration of STACK type questions and present the stages of experiences in writing process of tests questions using STACK in TTK UAS.

2 Background

TTK University of Applied Sciences (TTK UAS) is a state professional higher education institution, offering competitive professional higher education in the fields of engineering, production, technology, architecture and construction. TTK UAS is active in development of digital technologies. Since 2006, learning materials based on the Moodle platform options. The percentage of online-supported subjects in curriculums has increased every year. In 2016/2017 it was in average 51% (540 active online courses), 2017/2018 it was 63% (570 active online courses), and 2018/2019 it was 69% (approximately 600 active online courses) [Ye20].

At the Centre for Science, TTK UAS learning and teaching of all subjects are supported by a Moodle course with different types of theoretical materials, tests, videos and other online activities [UL17], [UL18]. At the university level, regular courses for teachers are provided to introduce methods for creating online tests.

The Centre for Science has been intensely and systematically using online tests at least in the last 4 years [La20], online self-tests and online assessment tests are an integral part of the learning process. Those provide opportunities for improving feedback and can be highly motivating for the students. [Ra10].

But, despite the constant development in the field of creating and testing online tests, two main problems arose that did not allow us to fully fulfil the pedagogical tasks. The first and biggest problem was the need for the student to enter mathematical expressions. And second one is the need to generate initial data of tests' questions. A solution to these problemes were discovered in 2017, with the help of the Future Math project launched in Finland, we found out about the existence of STACK. And in the same year, the Centre for Science had a reform in the volumes and contents of mathematical subjects (see Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: Changes in math subjects

So, academics of the Centre for Science, TTK UAS were forced to review and update the materials of courses in mathematics. STACK found a place in the updated tests, for today about 16% of all questions in the question bank are STACK questions.

3 Methodology

Mastering any skills is a process consisting of certain stages, each of which is based on the previous one. Analysing the process of working with the STACK system, we identified four main stages in exploring its capabilities: questions that allow students to enter an algebraical expressions, randomly generated one node questions using Maxima's random functions, randomly generated one node questions using Maxima commands from different branches of mathematics, randomly generated questions with many nodes.

3.1 Questions that allow students to enter an algebraical expressions

In the educational process of teaching mathematics in recent years, mainly self-tests and formative tests are used. In these tests, the main role is given to open-ended questions in order to avoid random answers for students. For this purpose, questions such as "Short answer", "Calculated", "Numerical", "Embedded answers" and "Gapfill" were used, where the student can either enter the final result, or some part of the solution, or complete the solution step by step. Unfortunately, open-ended assignments often generate several correct, but logically disproportionate answers, which is undesirable from the point of view of an unambiguous assessment and technological control. To prevent unwanted interpretations, certain agreements with students about the rules for entering answers were used, otherwise the system would not have considered the answer correct (see Fig. 2).

Leida funktsiooni $y=(1-x^8)/(1-x^2)$ tuletis

Vastus: ✓

Õige vastus on: $y'=(2x-8x^7-6x^9)/(1-x^2)^2$

Leida funktsiooni $y=(1-x^8)/(1-x^2)$ tuletis

Vastus: ✗

Õige vastus on: $y'=(2x-8x^7-6x^9)/(1-x^2)^2$

Fig. 2: Open-ended question

Sometimes restrictions are added to questions, such as "calculate to the nearest hundredth" or technical hints like "abs (x)", "sqrt (x)", as well as tooltips written using HTML code. To ensure variability for each question, an average of 8 versions was created. Versions of the questions were identical in content of the question but differed in the values of the source data.

The study of the STACK system began in connection with the need to provide students with the opportunity to write down answers in the form of mathematical expressions. Now the system accepts the student's final answer as correct, even if it is expressed in mathematically equivalent form (simplified or factorized) (see Fig. 3).

Fig. 3: Question that allow students enter an algebraical expressions

Moreover, the student receives feedback from the computer related to the response syntax. This gives the student the opportunity to avoid technical errors.

3.2 Randomly generated one node questions

At the next stage, the possibility of including parameters in test questions as random objects with a randomization function (and some of its modifications) of the Maxima computer algebra system (CAS) was considered. The STACK question from the previous figure (see Fig. 3) is now represented by the parameter, and as a result, eight variants of the question are obtained with $2 < a < 9$ (see Fig. 4).

Fig. 4: Randomly generated one node question with one parameter

In the general case, the correct STACK answer is generated using the initial data and functions of the Maxima CAS, but at this stage the correct answer was made using manually created expressions.

3.3 Randomly generated one node questions using Maxima commands from different branches of mathematics

During the third stage, the Maxima commands, which are necessary for analytical calculations, algebra and calculus were studied. It allowed us to take a new level in the creation of STACK questions, including also the randomization of the several parameters in test question (see Fig. 5).

Fig. 5: Randomly generated one node question with several parameters

It should be noted that all questions at this and previous stages contained one node. In these tasks, the student's mistake in the intermediate calculations leads to a zero result for the whole question. Therefore, all questions of the first three stages were used only in self-tests without credits and penalties. This is clearly seen on the example of tasks with matrices (see Fig. 6).

The screenshot shows a question titled 'Matema 1' asking for the result of $A - B + 3C$ given three matrices: $A = \begin{bmatrix} 2 & 1 & 3 \\ 0 & -4 & -2 \\ 3 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$, $B = \begin{bmatrix} -2 & 0 & 0 \\ 4 & -4 & -4 \\ 0 & -2 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$, and $C = \begin{bmatrix} -2 & 0 & 0 \\ 4 & -4 & -4 \\ 0 & -2 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$. The student's answer is $\begin{bmatrix} 6 & -10 & -4 \\ -4 & 8 & 4 \\ -2 & -10 & -4 \end{bmatrix}$. The system indicates that the first row is incorrect. The correct answer is $\begin{bmatrix} -6 & -10 & -4 \\ -4 & 8 & 4 \\ -2 & -10 & -4 \end{bmatrix}$.

Fig. 6: Partially correct answer

At the same time, the STACK question not only provides automatically generated feedback about correct and incorrect answers, but also visualizes partially correct answers, highlighting erroneous values in red.

3.4 Randomly generated questions with many nodes

At the last, fourth stage, questions with a multitude of nodes are constructed, which allow the test creator to build a tree of potential answers and thereby provide feedback and assessment for each node (see Fig. 7).

The screenshot shows a STACK question interface. On the left, a sidebar displays 'Küsimus 1', 'Osaliselt õige', and 'Hindapunkte 0.50/1.00'. The main area contains the question text: 'Antud $\vec{a} = 4\vec{i} + 4\vec{j}$. Leia vektor $\vec{b} \neq \vec{0}$, mis asub koordinaatide tasandi IV-s veerandis ja on risti vektoriga \vec{a} .' Below this is an input field for the answer, showing 'Vastus: $\vec{b} = 4$ $\vec{i} + (4) \vec{j}$ '. Two lines of feedback follow: 'Your last answer was interpreted as follows: 4' and 'Your last answer was interpreted as follows: 4'. A yellow feedback box contains the following text: 'Vastus on osaliselt õige. Vektorid ei ole risti. Kasutage punkti punktimiseks, et uurida, kas kaks vektorit on risti. Lahendus: Kaks vektorit on risti kui nende skalaarkorrutis on null. Kui $\vec{a} = 4\vec{i} + 4\vec{j} = (4, 4)$, siis vektor $\vec{b} = (4, -4)$ on risti vektoriga \vec{a} kuna $\vec{a} \cdot \vec{b} = 4 \cdot 4 + 4 \cdot (-4) = 0$. A correct answer is 4, which can be typed in as follows: 4. A correct answer is -4, which can be typed in as follows: -4.'

Fig. 7: Randomly generated questions with many nodes

One of the recommendations of the Estonian Higher Education Quality Agency regarding the study activities of higher education institutions is to apply more formative assessment in the study process, giving students meaningful feedback on learning outcomes and thus increasing their learning motivation [USM15]. Automatically generated feedback and scores for each node meet the goals of both independent and formative assessments, which allows using STACK questions in formative assessment as well.

4 Findings

The results of this study are divided into two parts: from the point of view of teachers and from the point of view of students.

Using STACK questions allows the teacher to reduce the volume of test tasks. If three years ago, to ensure variability, we created 6-8 options with different parameters for each question, but now we only need one or two questions with feedback generation and points on each node. Technically, we have no limitations, and we can build questions based on our needs, and not on the capabilities of the system. This approach diversify testing.

For students, using STACK questions provides an unlimited number of self-test attempts. Great help to students is provided by feedback. Firstly, it shows the form in which the answer was read by a computer and avoids technical errors. Secondly, the feedback associated with the parameters of a specific task and the ability to visualize incorrect answers helps students understand in which step the error occurs.

5 Conclusions and Plans

Academics of the Centre for Science, TTK UA found, that automatic self-test and assessment test using STACK questions is a highly significant approach, which has many useful applications in mathematics and STEM education at all. Main obstacles for teaching and learning mathematical subjects using online tests, namely, entering the answer as a mathematical expression, could be solved using STACK. With the help of STACK could be created a powerful feedback. Therefore, the authors also see STACK like an instrument for creating a learning models that give students immediate feedback and the opportunity for self-reflection. The STACK questions target use approach has been applied to all engineering mathematics courses in TTK UAS. The authors plan to increase the number of STACK questions.

In close collaboration with the faculties of the TTK UAS, a new elective subject "Geometry in Engineering" program was developed during spring 2020. As part of the teaching of this subject, the online Moodle course will be created, in spring of 2021 a new elective subject "Geometry in Engineering" will be launched. The authors have a definite plan for systematic use of STACK type questions for creating self-tests and assessment tests. For distance students pure e-learning method has been planned. Final product of academics' work will be an established database covering all basic topics in geometry used in engineering. Also, it is planned to create STACK questions that include graphs. The creation of such types of questions is a new direction for the Centre for Science, TTK UAS, but it is necessary activity, taking into account that the new subject is connected to geometry, where visualization plays an important role.

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